

Release of metals from coffee machines and electric kettles

BfR communication No 041/2015, 9 November 2015

No legal limits have so far been defined for the release of metals from metallic food contact materials. In 2013, the European Council recommended limit values for 21 metals and metalloids (Resolution CM/Res(2013)9). To investigate whether the metallic food contact objects available on the market comply with these limit values and whether the recommended analysis methods are suitable for ensuring compliance, the BfR conducted a research project.

As part of this ongoing project, different coffee machines and electric kettles were tested for their metal release. The BfR already reported the results of the study of coffee machines in 2013. Now these research results and the test method have been published in the journal *Food Additives & Contaminants*:

[Metal release from coffee machines and electric kettles](#)

Frederic D. Müller, Christin Hackethal, Roman Schmidt, Oliver Kappenstein, Karla Pfaff, Andreas Luch, *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A*, 32:11, 1959-1964, 2015

Link: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2015.1086929>

The full version of this BfR Communication is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/freisetzung-von-metallen-aus-kafeemaschinen-und-elektrischen-wasserkochern.pdf>